

Extension of Michael's Reaction. Part IV.

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In previous parts of this series (Ghosh and Guha, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1930, 7, 263) the action of mustard oils and isocyanates has been studied upon various types of compounds containing one active methylene group. It seemed desirable to extend this type of condensation with compounds containing more than one active methylene group. Acetone dicarboxylic ester, in which there are two active methylene groups, was expected to yield compounds of the type I and II respectively with one or two molecules of mustard oils or isocyanates.

(I)

(II)

An unsuccessful attempt to effect ring-closure of thiocarbethoxy-acetoacetyl carbamic ester with the aid of sodium ethoxide for pyridine ring synthesis has been recorded by Ghosh and Guha (*J. Ind. Inst. Sci.*, 1933, 16A, 103). The second object in undertaking the present investigation was to see whether arylcarbonylacetone dicarboxylic ester (type I) in presence of suitable ring-closing agents could be converted into a pyridine compound (III).

(III)

Ethylacetone dicarboxylate in presence of sodium (1 or 2 atoms) reacts with thiocarbimides (1 or 2 mols.) to give instead of the expected

ted thio analogues of compounds (I), (II) or (III), a thiopyran compound (IV) according to the following scheme:

The compound (Ia), which is evidently formed as the first product in this reaction, possesses such a great tendency towards ring formation that its isolation was not possible. That the ring-closed compound possesses the formula (IV) and is not the pyridine derivative of type (III) is proved by the facts that (a) it is not endowed with any mercaptanic properties, (b) it cannot be desulphurised by mercuric oxide treatment proving thereby the presence of the sulphur atom as a member of the ring (*cf.* Busch and Wolpert, *Ber.*, 1901, 34, 304; Guha, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1922, 44, 1502), (c) it gives on hydrolysis the compound (V).

The compound (IV) reacts with benzaldehyde to yield a compound which can be represented by either of the two following formulæ (VI or VIa). In view of the fact that the original compound (IV) gives a disodium derivative whereas the benzaldehyde compound does not form any sodium salt, the formula (VIa) is rejected in preference to the bridged formula (VI), enolisation of (VI) into (VIb) and (VIc) being against Bredt's law (*Annalen*, 1924, 437, 1).

(VIb)

(VIc)

This reaction affords a new and convenient method for the synthesis of thiopyran rings.

Ethylacetone dicarboxylate reacts with phenyl isocyanate to give the expected diphenylcarbamyloxy derivative (VII) which shows no tendency towards ring formation, this difference is evidently due to the thiocarbamyl groupings possessing greater capacity for ring formation.

(VII)

The compound (VII) containing as it does two active hydrogen atoms reacts readily with aldehyde to form the transient intermediate product (VIII) which gives with the elimination of alcohol a tricyclic compound (IX) or (IXa) depending on whether the elimination of alcohol takes place according to X or Y.

(VIII)

(IX)

(VIII)

The formula (IX) is preferred because a compound having a structure like (IXa), a combination of three four-membered spiro-rings, cannot be expected to be so stable. In accordance with the valency deflexion theory of Thorpe and Ingold (*J. Chem Soc.*, 1915, 107, 1080) the formation of the *cyclobutane* ring in compound (VIII) is attended with a widening of the angles α and β between A—B and C—D respectively as the result of which the groupings 'A and C' and 'B and D' come closer together and thus the elimination of alcohol takes place between 'A and C' and between 'B and D'.

The disodium derivative of ethylmethylene dimalonate reacts with phenyl isocyanate to yield the ring compound (X) and not the open-chain diphenylcarbamylmethylene dimalonic ester (Xa) as expected by analogy with compound (VII). This difference is perhaps due to the influence exerted by two pairs of carbethoxy groups in compound (Xa), bringing the two phenylcarbamyl groupings in closer proximity.

The compound (X) is acidic in nature forming monosodium salt. On mild hydrolysis it yields the compound (XI).

Ethyl ketipinate was allowed to react with phenyl isocyanate with the hope that the resulting product will react with aldehydes to yield a compound of the above type (IX). The reaction product could not, however, be obtained in a pure form.

The disodium derivative of ethyl 2:6-diketo-4:4-dimethylcyclohexane-3:5-dicarboxylate did not react with phenyl isocyanate; the ester was recovered unchanged from the reaction product.

It is worth while mentioning in this connection that an attempt was made to synthesise pyridine derivatives by condensing cinnamylideneacrylic ester with phenyl isocyanate following the method of Diels (*Annalen*, 1925, 443, 242; 1928, 460, 98; 1929, 470, 62), but the condensation, though tried under varying conditions of experiment, did not take place.

EXPERIMENTAL.

Ethyl 2-phenyliminothiopyran-4:6-dione-3-carboxylate (IV, R = Ph).—Sodium (2.3 g.) was gradually added to a solution of ethylacetone dicarboxylate (10.2 g.) in absolute ether (200 c. c.). The

evolution of hydrogen ceased after about 3 hours. The mixture after the addition of phenylmustard oil (7 g.) was allowed to stand overnight. The separated reddish brown precipitate was dissolved in water and acidified with dilute hydrochloric acid, when a brownish semi-solid mass was obtained which crystallised from benzene in colourless rectangular plates, m. p. 128-29° (decomp.), yield 8 g. [Found: N, 4.71; S, 11.04; M. W. (by titration), 293. $C_{14}H_{13}O_4NS$ requires N, 4.81; S, 10.99 per cent. M. W., 291]. It has been found by titration with standard caustic soda solution that it forms a disodium salt. It does not give any disulphide and is not desulphurised by oxide of mercury.

The same compound (IV) was obtained when phenylmustard oil (2 mols.) was allowed to react with ethylacetone dicarboxylate (1 mol.).

Ethyl 2-o-tolyliminothiopyran-4:6-dione-3-carboxylate (IV, R = *o-tolyl*) crystallised from benzene in colourless rectangular plates, m. p. 150° (decomp.). (Found: S, 10.32. $C_{15}H_{15}O_4NS$ requires S, 10.49 per cent).

Ethyl 2-p-tolyliminothiopyran-4:6-dione-3-carboxylate (IV, R = *p-tolyl*) was crystallised from benzene in colourless rectangular plates, m. p. 145° (decomp.). (Found: S, 10.38. $C_{15}H_{15}O_4NS$ requires S, 10.49 per cent).

2-o-Tolylimino-4:6-dione-thiopyran (V, R = *o-tolyl*).—4 G. of the compound (IV, R = *o-tolyl*) were heated under reflux with alcoholic potash (12%) for 8 hours and then diluted with water. The cooled solution, on acidification, gave a solid which crystallised from dilute acetic acid in brownish white rectangular plates, m. p. 210° (decomp.), yield 2 g. (Found: S, 14.01. $C_{12}H_{11}O_2NS$ requires S, 13.73 per cent). It is readily soluble in dilute alkali and can be precipitated by acids. It does not possess any mercaptanic properties.

2-p-Tolylimino-4:6-dione-thiopyran (V, R = *p-tolyl*) was crystallised from dilute acetic acid in brownish white rectangular plates, m. p. 214-15° (decomp.). (Found: S, 13.97. $C_{12}H_{11}O_2NS$ requires S, 13.73 per cent).

2-Phenylimino-4:6-dione-thiopyran-3:5-benzylidene-3-carboxylate (VI, R = *phenyl*).—An acetic acid solution of the compound (IV, R = *phenyl*; 3 g.) and benzaldehyde (1.2 g.) were heated under reflux for about an hour. On cooling, a yellow mass came out which

crystallised from acetic acid in yellowish white rectangular plates, m.p. 274-75°, yield 2.5 g. (Found: S, 8.65. $C_{21}H_{17}O_4NS$ requires S, 8.44 per cent). It is insoluble in alcohol, ether and alkali. The *monosemicarbazone* was obtained as a brownish white crystalline powder by heating the above compound with excess of semicarbazide acetate in dilute acetic acid solution, m.p. above 290°. (Found: N, 12.53. $C_{22}H_{20}O_4N_4S$ requires N, 12.84 per cent).

2-p-Tolylimino-4:6-dione-thiopyran-3:5-benzylidene-3-carboxylate (VI, R = *p-tolyl*) was crystallised from acetic acid in yellowish white rectangular plates, m.p. above 280°. (Found: S, 7.86. $C_{22}H_{19}O_4NS$ requires S, 8.14 per cent). It is insoluble in alkali.

Ethyl α' -phenylcarbonylacetone dicarboxylate (VII).—Sodium (2.3 g.) was gradually added to a solution of ethylacetone dicarboxylate (10.2 g.) in absolute ether (200 c.c.). After the evolution of hydrogen was over, phenyl isocyanate (12 g.) was added to the solution when at once the reaction began with evolution of heat. The precipitate was filtered overnight, dissolved in water and acidified with dilute hydrochloric acid and the separated solid crystallised from glacial acetic acid in colourless rectangular plates, m.p. 188-89°, yield 15 g. (Found: N, 6.36. $C_{23}H_{24}O_7N_2$ requires N, 6.36 per cent). It is readily soluble in dilute alkali and is precipitated by acids. When it was heated with acetic anhydride for about an hour a clear solution was obtained which, on treatment with sodium carbonate solution, yielded a tarry mass. This yielded a very small quantity of a colourless crystalline product (m.p. 226-27°) on being digested with ether.

Action of benzaldehyde upon compound (VII): Formation of compound (XI) (R = Ph).—To a boiling acetic acid solution of the compound (VII, 4.4 g.), benzaldehyde (1.1 g.) was added, the reaction starting at once with evolution of heat. The separated orange yellow crystalline mass crystallised from large quantity of glacial acetic acid in beautiful orange yellow needles, m.p. 247-48°(decomp.) yield 3.5 g. (Found: C, 71.80; H, 4.00; N, 6.53. $C_{26}H_{16}O_5N_2$ requires C, 71.56; H, 3.67; N, 6.42 per cent). It is insoluble in alcohol, benzene and alkali.

The *monosemicarbazone* was obtained in the usual manner and was crystallised from dilute acetic acid in brownish white rectangular plates, m.p. 214-15° (decomp.). (Found: N, 13.77. $C_{27}H_{19}O_5N_3$ requires N, 14.19 per cent).

Action of o-nitrobenzaldehyde upon compound (VII): Formation of compound (IX) (R = o-nitrophenyl).—The method of procedure was the same as in the case of the above compound. The product crystallised from large quantity of glacial acetic acid in beautiful orange yellow needles, m.p. 199-200° (decomp.). (Found: N, 8.85. $C_{26}H_{15}O_7N_3$ requires N, 8.73 per cent). It is insoluble in alkali.

α -Phenylcarbamido- $\alpha\alpha'$ -tricarbethoxy-N-phenylglutarimide (X) was obtained from ethylmethylene dimalonate and phenyl isocyanate exactly in the same manner as in the case of the compound (VII). The precipitate obtained from the reaction product by filtration next day was partly soluble in cold water; the insoluble portion, on crystallisation, was proved to be diphenylurea. The aqueous solution, on acidification with dilute hydrochloric acid, yielded a white precipitate which crystallised from alcohol in beautiful colourless shining needles, m.p. 123-24°. [Found: N, 5.14; M.W. (by titration), 532. $C_{27}H_{28}O_9N_2$ requires N, 5.34 per cent. M.W., 524]. It forms monosodium salt with alkali but is insoluble in sodium carbonate.

Hydrolysis of the compound (X): Formation of α -phenylcarbamido- $\alpha\alpha'$ -dicarboxy-N-phenylglutarimide (XI).—A solution of the compound (X) (4 g.) in N-alkali was kept at ordinary temperature for 24 hours and then heated on the water-bath for about half an hour, cooled and acidified with dilute hydrochloric acid when a white precipitate came down. It was purified by precipitation by acid from its solution in sodium bicarbonate. It crystallised from dilute alcohol in colourless plates, m.p. 180° (decomp.), yield 1.5 g. (Found: N, 7.15. $C_{20}H_{16}O_7N_2$ requires N, 7.07 per cent).

Action of phenyl isocyanate upon ketipinic ester.—To an ethereal suspension of the disodium derivative of ketipinic ester (prepared according to the method of Wislicenus, *Ber.*, 1887, 20, 589) phenyl isocyanate (2 mols.) was added. The reaction mixture, after being allowed to stand overnight, was poured into cold water. The ethereal layer, on evaporation, yielded a white solid which after crystallisation was identified to be diphenylurea. The aqueous layer, on acidification, yielded a very small quantity of a reddish brown tarry mass which could not be purified.

Action of phenyl isocyanate on ethyl 2:6-diketo-4:4-dimethylcyclohexane-3:5-dicarboxylate.—The method of procedure was the same as in the previous case. The ethereal layer yielded diphenylurea and the aqueous layer, on acidification, the original ester.

SUMMARY.

1. A thiopyran derivative, obtained by condensing ethylacetone dicarboxylate (1 mol.) with thiocarbimides (1 mol.) reacts with aldehydes to give bridged compounds.

2. Ethyl $\alpha\alpha'$ -phenylcarbamyacetone dicarboxylate obtained from ethylacetone dicarboxylate (1 mol.) and phenyl isocyanate (2 mols.) reacts with aldehydes to give tricyclic compounds.

3. Ethylmethylene dimalonate (1 mol.) reacts with phenyl isocyanate (2 mols.) to give α -phenylcarbamido- $\alpha\alpha'$ -tricarboethoxy-*N*-phenylglutarimide.

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